

EFFECT OF FLEXIBLE INTERPHASE ON DYNAMIC CHARACTERISTICS OF CFRP

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Keywords: *Flexible interphase, Fatigue characteristic, Fracture mechanism*

1 Introduction

Interface in Fiber Reinforced Plastics (FRP) is generally 2-dimensional boundary between fiber and matrix resin. The concept have been known that interface between fiber and matrix of FRP is regarded as “Interphase” which is 3 dimensional region having thickness and own mechanical property. Therefore, the mechanical properties of the composite can be positively controlled by the mechanical property of the interphase. For this purpose, interphase needs to be thick and gradient to utilize the performance of mechanical property of interphase. According to the concept, improvements of mechanical properties of FRP were succeed by giving interphase different property from matrix resin [1,2]. This interphase was called functional interphase.

Flexible interphase is one of the functional interphase. In this case, flexible resin was attached with thick and gradient phase around reinforcement fiber. Improvements of interfacial shear strength, tensile strength, and interlaminar fracture toughness of FRP were achieved by giving interphase different property especially more “flexible” properties than matrix resin. [3]

In this study, the effect of “flexible” interphase on static and dynamic characteristic of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) was examined by static tensile test, repeated tensile test, high cycle tensile fatigue test, drop weight impact test.

2 Fabrication of specimen with flexible interphase

Carbon cloth (HONLU TECHNOLOGY Co.LTD.) and epoxy resin (jER 828, Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) with hardner (jER cure W, Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) were used as reinforcements and matrix resin. Two different kinds of “flexible” epoxy resin (PB3600, and AT501, Daicel

corporation) were used for creation of flexible interphase. Here, flexible properties are defined as lower elastic modulus and higher breaking elongation than matrix resin. Mechanical properties of matrix resin and flexible resin are shown in Table 1. Tensile modulus and elastic elongation of matrix resin was 3.68GPa and 5.00%. Comparing matrix resin and flexible resin, elastic modulus of PB3600 was 2.40GPa which is lower than matrix resin, breaking elongation of PB3600 was 9.14% which is higher than matrix resin. Elastic modulus of AT501 was 0.49GPa which is lower than PB3600 and breaking elongation of AT501 was 88.3% which is higher than PB3600.

The flexible interphase was created by soaking carbon clothes in a solution of flexible resin and solvent for 10 seconds (flexible resin: solvent = X: (100 – X)). Acetone and ethyl acetate were used as solvent for flexible resin PB3600 and AT501 respectively. Treatment concentration is able to be modified by changing X. Then, the carbon clothes were dried at 80 degrees Celsius for 1 hour. Weight increasing rate of carbon cloth by flexible treatment as a function of the treated concentration is shown in Fig.1. Increasing rate increased with an increase in treated concentration in a proportional manner. Certain number of carbon clothes with flexible treatment were stacked on, and the matrix resin was impregnated by hand lay-up method. Then it was cured at 100 degrees Celsius for 2 hours and 175 degrees Celsius for 4 hours.

Table.1 Mechanical properties of matrix resin and flexible resin

Resin	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Breaking elongation (%)	TG (°C)
PB3600 (Flexible resin)	2.40	31.7	9.14	120
jER828 (Matrix resin)	3.68	74.0	5.00	160
AT501 (Flexible resin)	0.49	2.63	88.3	

Fig.1 Relationship between weight increasing rate by flexible treatment and treatment concentration

3 Specimen preparation and experimental

3.1 Static tensile test

Tensile test specimens were 2ply woven composites. Specimen was cut into 20mm in width and 200mm in length. Longitudinal direction of the specimen was corresponding to warp direction of woven fabric. Thickness of static tensile specimen was about 0.4mm. Treatment concentration was 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7wt% by PB3600 and 1, 2, 3, 4wt% by AT501. For comparison, two kinds of 0wt% specimens were prepared. One is non treated and the other is prepared by soaking carbon clothes in only acetone without flexible resin. Static tensile test was carried out by using TENSILON universal testing machine (RTC-1350A; ORIENTEC Co.,LTD.) . The testing speed was 1mm/min, and span length was 100mm.

3.2 Repeated tensile test

Repeated tensile test specimens were 12ply woven composites. Specimen was cut into 20mm in width and 200mm in length. Longitudinal direction of the specimen was corresponding to warp direction of woven fabric. Thickness of repeated tensile specimen was about 2.5mm. Treatment concentration was non treated and 5, 7wt% for PB3600 3wt% for AT501. Repeated tensile test was carried out by using TENSILON universal testing machine (RTC-1350A; ORIENTEC Co.,LTD.) . Span length was 100mm, and number of loading cycle was 100 cycles with testing speed of 1mm/min. Maximum cyclic load was 70% of maximum load that was obtained from static tensile test. Edge face of specimen was polished before the test, and in-situ

observation was carried out by using replica method to observe onset and progress of micro fractures under tensile loading.

3.3 High cycle tensile fatigue test

High cycle tensile fatigue test specimens were 6ply woven composites. Specimens were cut into 25mm in width and 200mm in length. Longitudinal direction of the specimen was corresponding to warp direction of woven fabric. Thickness of high cycle fatigue tensile specimen was about 1.2mm. Treatment concentration was non treated, 5wt% for PB3600 which shows highest value in static tensile test, and 10wt% which treatment concentration is double 5wt%. High cycle tensile fatigue test was carried out by using hydraulic servo testing machine (EHF-EV100K1-010-0A ; SIMADZU Corporation) . Testing speed was 10Hz, and span length was 100mm. Initial repeated testing stress was determined by JIS K 7083.

3.4 Drop weight impact test

Drop weight impact test specimens were 12ply woven composites. Specimens were cut into a square 100mm on a side. Thickness of drop weight impact specimen was about 2.5mm. Treatment concentration was non treated, 5wt% for PB3600 and 4wt% for AT501. Drop weight impact test was carried out by using impact testing machine (Instron Dynatup 9250HV ; Instron JAPAN Co.,LTD.) . A specimen was fixed by plate having 76mm hole in diameter and load was applied by hemispherical indenter with 12.7mm in radius. Applied energy was 40J.

4 Result and discussion

4.1 Static tensile test

Relationship between stress and strain for PB3600 is shown in Fig.2. Relationship between strength and treatment concentration is shown in Fig.3 . For PB3600, tensile strength of all treatment concentration is higher than non treated. Tensile strength increased with increase in treatment concentration up to 5wt%, and it decreased over 5wt%. For AT501, tensile strength increased when treated concentration is 1wt% comparing to non treated. Tensile strength showed constant value over

1wt%. From those results, it was clarified that there is an optimum value for treated concentration.

Fig.2 Relationship between stress and strain (PB3600)

Fig.3 Relationship between strength and treatment concentration

4.2 Repeated tensile test

The result of cross-sectional observation by replica method is shown in Fig.4. These pictures were typical observation results of non treated (at 20, 80, 100 cycles) and 7wt% (at 30, 70, 100 cycles) specimens. From these results, transverse cracks in 90 degree fiber bundles, delamination around 90 fiber bundles, and filament fracture in a 0 fiber bundles were observed in both specimens.

The relationship between length of transverse crack in 90 fiber bundles, length of delamination around 90 fiber bundles, number of filament fracture in 0

fiber bundle, and number of loading cycle are shown in Fig.5, Fig.6 and Fig.7. From these results, length of transverse crack, length of delamination, and number of filament fracture for flexible treated specimens were less than non treated one. Comparing 5wt% and 7wt% of treated concentration, 5wt% and 7wt% showed similar tendency but was less than that of 5wt%. In the case of 3wt% of AT501, each value showed almost the same as 5wt% of PB3600.

From these results, a schematic depiction of micro fracture progression shows in Fig.8. Each initial fracture was transverse crack in 90 fiber bundles. In the case of non treated specimen, transverse cracks generated and propagate through 90 fiber bundles in relatively lower loading cycle. As number of loading cycle increased, these transverse cracks progressed into interface around 90 fiber bundles. On the other hand, in the case of flexible treated specimen, shorter transverse cracks in 90 fiber bundles occurred. Then number of transverse cracks increased with increase in number of loading cycle. After that, some of transverse cracks progressed through 90 fiber bundles, and into interface around 90 fiber bundles. From these results, it was clarified that fracture mechanism was changed by flexible treatment. Progression of transverse cracks, delamination around 90 fiber bundles, filament fracture in a 0 fiber bundles were restrained by flexible interphase.

Fig.4 Observation result by replica method (Non treated, 7wt% flexible treated)

Fig.5 Relationship between length of transverse cracks in 90 fiber bundles and number of loading cycle

Fig.6 Relationship between length of delamination around 90 fiber bundles and number of loading cycle

Fig.7 Relationship between number of filament fracture in 0 fiber bundle and number of loading cycle

(a) Non treated

(b) Flexible treated

Fig.8 Schematic depiction of micro fracture progression

4.3 High cycle tensile fatigue test

Relationship between maximum applied stress and number of cycles in high cycle tensile fatigue test is shown in Fig.9. Number of cycles of flexible treated specimen is higher than non treated specimen at the same maximum applied stress. Comparing flexible treated specimen, number of cycles of 10wt% is higher than 5wt% at the same maximum applied stress.

Cross section of specimen after high cycle tensile fatigue test at 510MPa for each specimens are shown in Fig.10. Transverse crack and delamination were seen in non treated specimen. Progression of transverse crack to delamination is also seen in non treated specimen. There aren't many micro fractures like non treated in 5wt%. Transverse crack and delamination were seen in 10wt% like non treated specimen. But delamination was less than non treated specimen.

Observation picture by scanning electron microscope for each specimens are shown in Fig.11. Comparing non treated specimen and flexible treated specimen, length of fiber pull-out for flexible treated specimen is less than non treated specimen. From cross section after high cycle tensile fatigue tensile test and observation picture by SEM, schematic depiction of micro fracture was made and shown in Fig.12. Many delaminations are seen in non treated

specimen. Length of fiber pull-out of non treated specimen is longer than flexible treated specimen. For flexible treated specimen, delamination was restrained by flexible interphase and length of fiber pull-out is less than non treated specimen. From those results, micro fracture was restrained by flexible interphase and flexible interphase is effective for long term durability.

Fig.9 Relationship between maximum applied stress and number of cycles

Fig.10 Cross section of specimen after high cycle tensile fatigue test at 510MPa

a. Non treated

b. 5wt%

c.10wt%

Fig.11 Observation picture by scanning electron microscope

a. Non treated

b. 5wt%

c. 10wt%

Fig.12 Schematic depiction of micro fracture

4.4 Drop weight impact test

Load and deflection for non treated is shown in Fig.13. 1st peak is the point which load starts to decrease. Max load is the point which load is at peak. Load and deflection for PB3600 and AT501 is shown in Fig.14 and Fig.15. Energy that calculated by Fig.13, 14, 15 is shown in Table 2. Energy to 1st peak is absorbed energy during elastic deformation of composites. Energy after 1st peak is absorption energy to break composites. From Table 1, max load increased about 20% for PB3600, 5% for AT501 compared with non treated. Total energy increased about 40% for PB3600, 15% for AT501. Cross section of specimen after drop weight impact test is shown in Fig.16. Fracture of fiber bundle, transverse crack and delamination were seen in non treated and AT501 specimen. Transverse crack and delamination were seen in PB3600. Relationship between length of fracture of fiber bundle, length of

delamination, length of transverse crack and treatment concentration are shown in Fig.17. There is little difference between length of fracture of fiber bundle and treatment concentration. Length of delamination increased with increase in treatment concentration. There is little difference length of transverse crack. Relationship between energy after 1st peak, total energy and length of delamination are shown in Fig.18. From result of cross section of specimen after impact test and relationship between delamination and treatment concentration, length of delamination increased with increase in treatment concentration, as a result absorption energy increased.

Fig.14 Relationship between load and deflection (PB3600)

Fig.13 Relationship between load and deflection (non treated)

Fig.15 Relationship between load and deflection (AT501)

Flexible treatment	Energy to 1st peak (J)	Energy after 1st peak (J)	Total Energy (J)	Max Load (kN)
Non treatment	2.19	16.44	18.64	2.15
PB3600_5wt%	3.48	22.59	26.1	2.62
AT501_4wt%	1.95	19.62	21.6	2.24

Table.2 Result of drop weight impact test

a. Non treated

b. AT501

c. PB3600

Fig.16 Cross section of specimen after drop weight impact test

a. Relationship between length of fracture of fiber bundle and treatment concentration

b. Relationship between length of delamination and treatment concentration

c. Relationship between length of transverse crack and treatment concentration

Fig.17 Relationship between each length of micro fracture and treatment concentration

a. Relationship between energy after 1st peak and length of delamination

b. Relationship between total energy and length of delamination

Fig.18 Relationship between each energy and length of delamination

5 Conclusion

In this study, CFRP with flexible interphase were made by using flexible resin which has lower elastic modulus and higher breaking elongation than matrix resin. The effect of flexible interphase on dynamic characteristic of CFRP was examined by static tensile test, drop weight impact test, repeated tensile test, high cycle tensile fatigue test. In static tensile test, flexible treated specimen with PB3600 and AT501 improved static tensile strength. PB3600 is more effective than AT501. In repeated tensile test, progression of transverse cracks, delamination around 90 fiber bundles, filament fracture in a 0 fiber bundles were restrained by flexible interphase. From result of repeated tensile test, it was clarified that fracture mechanism was changed by flexible treatment. In high cycle tensile fatigue test, micro fracture was restrained by flexible interphase and it was considered that flexible interphase is effective for long term durability. In drop weight impact test, max flexible treated specimen increased max load and total energy. From result of drop weight impact test, length of delamination increased with increase in treatment concentration, as a result absorption energy increased. It was clarified that static and dynamic characteristics of CFRP improved by flexible interphase.

References

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